

Toward a revised checklist of the Western Palearctic butterflies, hyperlinked to the original descriptions at species, genus and family level (Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea)

Part IV: Rationale and framework for the Riodinidae and Lycaenidae (part I)

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Abstract

Taxonomic and nomenclatural issues concerning the butterfly families Riodinidae and Lycaenidae (partim) are reviewed in light of the rules of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN), historical classifications, recent phylogenetic studies and current usage. Particular attention is given to the classification of subfamilies and tribes, where older names and synonymies have sometimes conflicted with prevailing usage, requiring rigorous evaluation under the Code.

The classification all species of the genera and subgenera of the tribe Lycaenini is debated and justified, particularly for the species *alciphron*, *hippotoe*, and *candens*. The status of the species *Lycaena dimorphus* (Staudinger, 1881) are clarified. *Lycaena japhetica* Nekrutenko & Effendi, 1983 is added to the checklist.

Key words

Taxonomy — Checklist — Papilionoidea — Lycaenidae — Riodinidae — Lycaeninae — Theclinae — Aphnaeinae — Lycaenin — *Lycaena* — *Cigaritis* — *Thecla* — *Favonius* — *Laeosopis* — *Deudorix* — *Tomares* — *Callophrys* — *Neolycaena* — *Satyrium* — *Lycaena dimorphus* — *Lycaena japhetica* — Western Palearctic.

Introduction

The present article seeks to clarify the classification adopted in the checklist for the family Riodinidae and for the subfamilies of the family Lycaenidae, with the exception of Polyommatinae, which will be addressed in a subsequent paper. Despite extensive research, the internal classification of this family remains partly unresolved. In particular, the rank and delimitation of the principal groups traditionally regarded as subfamilies have been interpreted in different ways by different authors, depending on the morphological or molecular evidence on which their conclusions are based. Over the past decades, several phylogenetic studies have proposed different hypotheses regarding the relationships among these groups. Analyses based on morphological characters or molecular data have produced alternative arrangements of the principal clades and have sometimes attributed to them different taxonomic ranks, treating them either as subfamilies or as tribes within broader assemblages. Consequently, no single classification has yet achieved general consensus, and the placement and relationships of some groups remain uncertain. Furthermore, some recent phylogenetic studies have delimited genera primarily on the basis of genetic data, sometimes without considering other criteria, which may lead to a certain degree of nomenclatural instability.

1. Classification of families and subfamilies

1.1 Riodinidae

The Riodinids, long treated as a subfamily of the Lycaenidae, are here regarded as a distinct family, following Espeland *et al.* (2015). This study places the genus *Hamearis* (the only West Palearctic genus of this family) within the tribe Nemeobiini of the subfamily Nemeobiinae.

The present checklist therefore follows Espeland *et al.* (2015) for the classification of the Riodinidae.

1.2. Lycaenidae

Among the Lycaenids, only the subfamilies Lycaeninae, Aphnaeinae and Theclinae are analysed in the present article. The subfamily Polyommatinae, which comprises a large number of tribes, genera and species, will be treated in a subsequent paper.

The classification adopted in the checklist follows the results of recent publications on classification and phylogeny produced over the last fifty years. Over time, the validity of the subfamilies and their relationships have been the subject of several hypotheses that differ markedly from one another. A representative sample is given below:

- Eliot, 1973: (Lipterinae + Poritiinae) + (Liphyrinae + Miletinae) + Curetinae + (Theclinae + Lycaeninae + Polyommatainae).
- Pierce *et al.*, 2002: Riodininae + (Poritiinae + Miletinae + Curetinae + Lycaeninae*) *including Theclini + Aphnaeini + Lycaenini + Polyommataini.
- Heikkilä *et al.*, 2012: Curetinae + (Lycaeninae** + (Aphnaeinae + Miletinae + Poritiinae)) **including Theclini + Lycaenini + Polyommataini.
- Liu *et al.*, 2020: Curetinae + ((Aphnaeinae + Miletinae) + (Lycaeninae + (Polyommatainae + Theclinae))).
- Wiemers *et al.*, 2020 (Europe only): (Aphnaeinae + Lycaeninae) + (Theclinae + Polyommatainae).
- Kawahara *et al.*, 2023: Curetinae + (Miletinae + ((Aphnaeinae + Poritiinae) + (Lycaeninae + (Theclinae + Polyommatainae)))).
- Zhang *et al.*, 2023: ((Liphyrinae + Miletinae) + (Poritiinae + Aphnaeinae)) + (Lycaeninae + (Theclinae + Polyommatainae)).

Recent phylogenetic studies of the Lycaenidae (Liu *et al.*, 2020; Wiemers *et al.*, 2020; Kawahara *et al.*, 2023) yield somewhat different results regarding the relationships among the subfamilies.

However, the subfamilies considered valid are the same, namely, for the West Palaearctic fauna: Aphnaeinae, Lycaeninae, Theclinae and Polyommatainae.

These four subfamilies have therefore been retained in the checklist. In the most recent studies, the position of the subfamily Aphnaeinae remains somewhat uncertain. It is therefore likely that the arrangement of the subfamilies will need to be revised in a future update of the checklist, based on further studies.

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2. Classification of tribes and genera

2.1. Subfamily Aphnaeinae

The West Palaearctic fauna of Aphnaeinae comprises only a few species, all associated with the genus *Cigaritis*. In a study of the global phylogeny of Aphnaeinae, Boyle *et al.* (2014) proposed a

revised generic structure without subgeneric divisions; the genus *Cigaritis* remains valid for all West Palaearctic species. In Zhang *et al.* (2023), the subfamily is divided into several tribes (mostly newly established); the genus *Cigaritis* is assigned to the tribe Cigaritini Grishin, 2023, trib. nov. This arrangement needs to be taken into account in a future version of the checklist. Weidenhoffer & Bozano (2007), who consider *Cigaritis* belonging to the tribe Aphnaeini within the subfamily Theclinae, divide the genus *Cigaritis* into three subgenera: *Cigaritis* Donzel, 1847, *Apharitis* Riley, 1925 and *Sphindasis* Wallengren, 1857; only the first two include West Palaearctic species. In that study, *C. myrmecophila* Dumont, 1922 and *C. acamas* (Klug, 1834) are placed in the subgenus *Apharitis*. However, the genitalia structure of these two species is very similar to that of the other species of the genus. The checklist therefore treats all species within the single genus (and subgenus) *Cigaritis*, in accordance with the results of the above-mentioned phylogenetic studies.

2.2. Subfamily Lycaeninae

Several studies have addressed the phylogeny of this subfamily (Cassulo *et al.*, 1989; Marabuto *et al.*, 2023; Walia *et al.*, 2025; etc.), but most have been either partial or based on a limited number of species. A recent study (Zhang *et al.*, 2022) provides a very comprehensive overview, including the type species of all taxa at the generic level. For the West Palaearctic species, this results in the following structure:

Genus *Lycaena* with the subgenera *Heodes**, *Alciphronia*, *Lycaena* and *Thersamolycaena* + genus *Helleia* with the subgenus *Helleia* + genus *Tharsalea* with five subgenera, of which only one is West Palaearctic, *Phoenicurusia*.

**Heodes* consists of two distinct clades, the *Heodes* sensu stricto clade and the *hippotoe/candens* clade, which was nevertheless retained within the subgenus *Heodes*.

In order to avoid fragmenting the genus *Lycaena*, and primarily in the interest of nomenclatural stability, the checklist does not follow the conclusions of this latter study. Instead, all species are retained within a single genus, *Lycaena*, with subgenera composed of species sharing a homogeneous genitalia structure.

This arrangement largely corresponds to the clades defined above by Zhang *et al.* (2022), with the exception of the following species:

L. hippotoe (Linnaeus, 1761) and *L. candens* (Herrich-Schäffer, [1844]), placed in the subgenus *Heodes* Dalman, 1816 by Zhang *et al.* (2022), are treated in a distinct subgenus, *Palaeochrysophanus* Verity, 1943, in the checklist. This is justified by the markedly different structure of their genitalia and by the fact that these two species form a distinct clade from the other species of *Heodes*.

L. alciphron (Rottemburg, 1775), placed in a separate subgenus, *Alciphronia* Koçak, 1992, by Zhang *et al.* (2022), is included in the subgenus *Heodes* Dalman, 1816 in the checklist. This is justified by the very similar genitalia structure shared with the other species of *Heodes*.

2.3. Subfamily Theclinae

Apart from Zhang *et al.* (2023) and Kawahara *et al.* (2023), no study has addressed the subfamily Theclinae as a whole, despite its high species richness and worldwide distribution. Consequently, no comparative data could be found for the two West Palaearctic genera *Favonius* and *Neolycaena*.

For the remaining genera, their placement in the checklist follows the two studies cited above. The two uncertain genera were assigned based on similarities in genitalia structure with the classified genera: *Favonius* is placed in the tribe Theclini and *Neolycaena* in the tribe Eumaeini.

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3. Notes on the status of *Lycaena dimorphus* (Staudinger, 1881)

3.1. Context

Nekrutenko & Effendi (1983) described *Lycaena japhetica* as a new species in the *Lycaena phoenicurus* (Lederer, 1872) group, from the valley of the Dizavarchay River in Azerbaijan.

Nekrutenko (1985) described *Lycaena japhetica irghiza*, a new subspecies, from the Aktobe River in the Irgiz region of Kazakhstan.

Lukhtanov (2000), in a study of this group of *Lycaena*, retained the specific status of *japhetica* but transferred its subspecies *irghiza* to *Lycaena dimorpha* (Staudinger, 1881).

Tshikolovets (2003), in his book on the butterflies of Eastern Europe, included *Lycaena japhetica* and indicated three localities on its distribution map: one in Azerbaijan and two in the Irgiz region of Kazakhstan, referring to Nekrutenko & Effendi (1983) and Nekrutenko (1985).

Lvovsky & Morgun (2007) reported the presence of *Lycaena dimorpha irghiza* in Orenburg Oblast (southern Urals, Russian Federation), relatively close to the border with Kazakhstan.

Wiemers *et al.* (2018) included *Lycaena dimorpha* (Staudinger, 1881) in their checklist, based on the record published by Lvovsky & Morgun (2007).

Following Wiemers *et al.* (2018), Taymans & Cuvelier (2023) included this species in the checklist under its original, non-agreement form *Lycaena dimorphus* (Staudinger, 1881).

Tshikolovets (2025) mentioned *Lycaena japhetica irghiza* from the Orenburg region (southern Urals, Russian Federation) and clearly justified his choice of species, correctly noting that Lukhtanov (2000) did not provide a valid justification for the species transfer he proposed. Moreover, the habitus and the male and female genitalia of *L. japhetica* differ markedly from those of *L. dimorpha* and in fact show closer similarity to *L. athamantis*.

As the diagnosis provided by Tshikolovets (2025) appears convincing, *Lycaena dimorphus* (Staudinger, 1881) will be removed from the checklist and replaced by *Lycaena japhetica* Nekrutenko & Effendi, 1983.

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Michel Taymans: conceptualisation, analysis, visualisation, writing - original draft, writing – review and editing.

Sylvain Cuvelier: analysis, validation, visualisation, writing – review and editing.

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